

POLICY BRIEF

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FROM MINING POLICY TO WATER (IN) SECURITY OF THE TERRITORIES: THE INTERAGENCY CONSULTATION AND THE ROLE OF THE STATE IN THE DEFENSE OF REGENERATIVE DEVELOPMENT.

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POLICY STATEMENT

From the perspective of the coevolution of the socioeconomic and environmental systems (1), the integrated and regenerative territorial development approach enables to visualize and to make compatible the different decision levels to achieve economic growth with social equity and environmental sustainability. Although mining contributes to economic development, it causes, on a large scale, great environmental and social harm by damaging ecosystem services that provide mainly water, food, fuel, medicine, and household. Since water is a fundamental requirement for the development of mining activities and, at the same time, the means by which climate change influences ecosystems, inter-agency articulation in the management and sustainable development of water resources becomes essential. This articulation allows us to prepare the abilities necessary in the whole society to confront climate change.

BACKGROUND

Mining is one of the sectors considered a catalyst for the development of a region and/or country. However, there are controversies regarding its effective role for the development of the territorial spaces where it operates. On the one hand, it is argued that the activity generates incomes that end up limiting the expansive capacity of other productive sectors as well as the permanence in power of backward and parasitic elites who are unable to implement policies to diversify the economy and make it less dependent on the mineral sector. On the other hand, the mineral sector is perceived as capable of generating the means to promote development since it generates large financial resources (2). In the context of the concept of sustainability of development – which warns of the imperative need to include future generations in present decisions and thus promote economic growth committed to ecosystem limits and social equity (3) – the opportunities are considered, but also the challenges that mining-based regions need to face to overcome obstacles.

E While sustainability refers to a long-term goal (i.e., a more sustainable world), sustainable development refers to the processes and pathways to achieve that sustainability. From such a perspective, in 2015, government and state leaders from 193 countries started a process by taking on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals – 17 SDGs, i.e., a global action plan to eliminate extreme poverty and hunger; provide lifelong quality education for all; protect the planet and promote peaceful and inclusive societies by 2030.

Focusing on SDG 13, “Action on Global Climate Change”, I highlight the importance of interagency consultation in the efficient management of water resources. The United Nations World Water Development Report (WWDR) finds that freshwater consumption has increased 6 times over the last century and continues to advance at a rate of 1% per year, boosted by a combination of population growth, socio economic development, and changing consumption patterns (4; 5). Most of this increase is concentrated in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in emerging economies. Water scarcity is becoming endemic as a result of the local impact of physical water stress, coupled with accelerating and spreading freshwater pollution. As a result of climate change, seasonal water shortages will increase in regions where water is currently abundant, such as Central Africa, East Asia, and parts of South America, and worsen in regions where water availability is already low, such as the Middle East and the Sahel in Africa. On average, 10% of the world's population lives in countries with high or critical water stress (UNESCO: 2023, p. 2). Therefore, it is important to recognize the value of water in its various dimensions and to incorporate such intrinsic and intangible values into policy actions and investments in the sector.

Mining is an activity completely dependent on the use of water (mining, processing and transport of ores configuring the use of the resource during the whole production process) and its viability is directly linked to the availability of water resources. Despite being a strategic sector for the global economy, undeniable climate change has imposed several risks and challenges on the management of mining projects and operations, and in particular the management of water and abandoned sites of mining companies (6). From a hydrological perspective, it is important to understand the effect that climate change will have on peak rainfall and its effect on mining infrastructure over 20, 100 and 200 years. Such as, for example, the return of flood events, including hydraulic modeling of flooding, strongly impacting landmarks on facilities such as tailings dams and tailings dumps (6). Other relations to climate change are the large use of fossil fuels in excavation operations or electricity in ore processing (7), which requires possible and urgent efforts to mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with a view to some degree of climate security in the future and adaptation to new and unavoidable environmental realities.

By taking responsibility for part of the world's GHG emissions, the mining industry has a commitment to reduce emissions urgently, since the sector has a large share of its largest projects in regions already suffering from water shortages. Although some territories are vulnerable, the advance of the mining frontier continues to be promoted by the public authorities and the private sector in several countries with significant mineral reserves, under the argument of sustainable development. Nevertheless, in the light of the little or unmitigated environmental impacts and of the expressive and often heightened social conflicts, this advance turns out to be the opposite of the alleged sustainability.

FINDINGS

Faced with the global adoption of the 17 SDGs, in 2016, the report *Mapping Mining to the Sustainable Development Goals: An Atlas* was published. The map illustrates how mining may positively influence the achievement of the SDGs, including considering the possibility of GHG emissions reduction by companies, from implementation plans associated with these goals (8). In 2017, the Portuguese version of the *Atlas* was launched, proposing the analysis of the relationship between mining activities and the 17 SDGs, with examples of concrete actions for scaling up and replication by stakeholders (10).

The RMI Report 2020 evaluates the actions in the areas of mining, policies, and practices of 38 large-scale mining companies around the world that together account for about 28% of the global value of mining production. It was concluded that although most of the world's large mining companies mention the SDGs in their sustainability reports, and although some pioneering companies have integrated them into their business strategies, most of the information disclosed about the SDGs by companies is purely cosmetic. There is still a scarcity of public disclosures about the negative impacts of companies on progress toward meeting the goals. As long as the reports remain unbalanced, there is a real risk that companies will be accused of SDG-Washing (the practice of only mentioning positive contributions towards the SDGs and ignoring negative ones).

In terms of companies' practical measures to support the achievement of the SDGsⁱⁱ, some companies distinguished themselves by performing relatively better than their peers within the sample of 38 mining companies studied. Nevertheless, there are notable differences between the measures supporting the SDGs that companies were able to demonstrate they have implemented and how they prioritize those same SDGs. For example, although SDG 3 (Health and Well-being) and SDG 6 (Safe Drinking Water and Sanitation) are among the most frequently prioritized SDGs and the most highlighted in materiality analysis, the report revealed that some of the weakest levels of performance by mining companies were precisely with respect to these SDGs (9).

In 2022, the Brazilian Portuguese version of the Methodological Guide: Building Bridges between the SDGs and Mining was published. In a collaborative way, opportunities were mapped, gaps in relation to the SDGs were assessed, and a financial assessment of selected projects that enhance the advancement of the SDGs in the business of mining companies was carried out. The document provides contributions from initiatives in the Brazilian territory, highlighting the sector's performance in the 2030 Agenda, with information about the actions that contributed to each of the 17 SDGs (11). Further research is needed on the capillarity of these actions in the territories and their implication on the socioeconomic, environmental, cultural, and political sustainability of development.

Iron ore deposits are concentrated in just five countries, which hold 77% of the total occurrences. Among them, Brazil holds the fifth largest reserve in the world, 8.3% of it, equivalent to 17 billion tons. With 19% of production, it is the second largest iron ore producer in the world, after China, which has 21% of production. The largest Brazilian deposits are in the state of Minas Gerais, with 61.2% of the national reserves; Mato Grosso do Sul, with 28.1% and Pará, with 10.4%. In Minas Geraisⁱⁱⁱ, there are three of Brazil's eight main iron-ore districts, located in the Iron Quadrangle^{iv}, the Eastern Edge of the Serra do Espinhaço and the Nova Aurora Iron District (12). We highlight the water issue in the Iron Quadrangle and the Eastern Edge of the Serra do Espinhaço.

In the Iron Quadrangle, the Serra do Gandarela form with the Serra do Caraça a natural corridor with a significant extension of Atlantic Forest and *Campos Rupestres* over *Cangas*^v. In addition to the environmental heterogeneity and the diverse plant physiognomies found in *cangas*, it is noteworthy the underground systems – ferruginous caves – associated with it which shelters an invertebrate community of extreme structural complexity. In a complementary way, Serra do Gandarela has an estimated storage of 1.6 trillion liters of drinking water, which led the Movement for the Preservation of Serra do Gandarela to name the region as Aquifer Quadrangle in a clear dispute of meaning regarding the naturalization of the mineral tradition of the region expressed by the hegemonic denomination (13)^{vi}.

Mineral exploration in Serra do Gandarela will cause irrecoverable loss of biodiversity in the region and destruction of part of the Ribeirão da Prata Basin, which contributes to the supply of the Belo Horizonte metropolitan region. Additionally, there will be significant impacts on its geological/geomorphological formation with serious damage to the hydrogeological system that constitutes the system of water resources responsible for the public supply of several municipalities (14). Mining activities in Serra do Gandarela would destroy the aquifers because to operate them it is necessary to remove the *canga* layer, discarded as 'sterile' (15). By removing the layer that absorbs and filters rainwater, the water recharging is stopped, and the environmental balance is altered. Another layer that would also be removed is the *itabirito*, where the iron ore is located. Since it is in this layer that water is stored and circulates toward the springs, the pumping of water required by mining would alter its flow and the supply of several regions. Several resorts in the region depend on the integrity of the Serra (16).

On October 13, 2014, through a presidential decree, the Serra do Gandarela National Park^{vii} was created, but with an area 20% smaller than suggested by the environmental technicians involved. The outer area corresponds to the area of interest of Vale S/A and of water recharge, rich in *canga* formations (17). Despite the arguments raised and the public actions carried out, in the creation of the Park and later in the resistance to the mining projects of the company, the preservation of the Aquiferous Quadrangle will not be fully achieved.

In 2008, Vale S.A. acquired the mining and surface rights belonging to Mineração Apolo in the municipalities of Rio Acima and Caeté in the Iron Quadrangle region. The Apolo Project, which had its licensing resumed in 2021, "consists in the opening of a mine with a production capacity of 24 million tons of iron ore per year and the implementation of a processing plant for the raw material in the municipalities of Caeté and Santa Bárbara, in the Central Region of the state" (14). Among others, in addition to the pit and the plant,

a new railroad branch will be built, about 20 km long, to transport the steel input to the Vitória-Minas Railroad (18).

The Iron Quadrangle, in geographic or geomorphological terms, is a continuation of the Serra do Espinhaço, recognized as a Biosphere Reserve in 2005 for its biodiversity and historic and cultural heritage. In 2008, at the eastern edge of the Espinhaço South, a transition zone of the Serra do Espinhaço Biosphere Reserve, the state government licensed Anglo American's Minas-Rio project. The area of implementation of the large mine and part of the pipeline comprises about 3,880 hectares, directly affecting the municipalities of Conceição do Mato Dentro (CMD), Alvorada de Minas, Dom Joaquim and Serro. The pipeline structure has 529 km and the capacity to transport 26.5 million tons of iron ore per year from the mining municipality of CMD to the Porto do Açu, in São João da Barra, Rio de Janeiro, crossing 33 cities. The estimated water demand is 3,123mm³/h taken mainly from the Rio do Peixe, one of the main tributaries of the Rio Doce Basin, in the municipality of Dom Joaquim (19)^{viii}

The use of water resources in the region is one of the main problems identified by organized groups of the communities directly affected by the projects and by environmental organizations interested in the process. This is mainly because water safety is not guaranteed in the face of climate change and other mining projects planned for the region, such as the Serpentine Project, of Vale S. A. The project foresees the construction of another pipeline of approximately 115 kilometers, leaving CMD and heading towards the railway yard located in the municipality of Nova Era, also impacting the municipalities of Dom Joaquim; Morro do Pilar; Carmésia; Santo Antônio do Rio Abaixo; São Sebastião do Rio Preto; Itambé do Mato Dentro; Passabém; Santa Maria de Itabira and Antônio Dias. According to the EIA/EIR (20), in addition to the pipeline, which will capture a large volume of water from the Rio Santo Antônio – which is of even greater concern to the communities, since it may have serious impacts on the Rio Doce basin^{ix} - the mining operation foresees the lowering of the water table with direct impact on more than 30 springs "inventoried in the modeled area and in water courses in the surroundings of the mineshafts".

Four pipelines are in operation with water withdrawal from rivers in the state of Minas Gerais, three of them belonging to Samarco and one to Anglo American^x, and two from the companies Ferrous and Manabi. The latter are in the environmental licensing phase with the Brazilian Institute for the Environment (21). The four mining projects in the state, which have pipelines to transport the iron ore, have a water collection permit sufficient to supply a city of 1.6 million inhabitants. The use of water by the pipelines stands out because often there is no reuse of the water resource, which is discarded into the sea (22).

If, on the one hand, pipelines are considered transportation modes among the most efficient in terms of logistics, on the other hand, their installation and operation result in impacts, conflicts, and socio-environmental disasters such as the one that occurred with the Anglo-American pipeline in 2018 (23). Regarding the water impact, between 2013 and 2015, the state of Minas Gerais had low rainfall rates. This scenario led to a significant reduction in the levels of reservoirs and the managing bodies, especially the Minas Gerais Sanitation Company – COPASA, were not able to meet the water demands of the population in several municipalities, generating a supply crisis in most of the state. This scenario was defined by the managing agencies as a supposed "water crisis", even though the causes are natural and cyclical. The reduction in water availability contradicts the traditional arguments of the State and the mining sector, which defends the pipelines as the best option for ore transportation with fewer environmental implications.

This issue was the subject of intense discussion among politicians, technicians, and environmentalists in the Legislative Assembly of Minas Gerais. The debates and questionings focused mainly on the volumes of water granted for the pipelines with the complication of the various legislative spheres involved in the licensing process (JUNIOR et.al: 2020, p. 350). In addition to the mining sector, the cumulative impact of water consumption with respective soil degradation promoted by other economic activities in the territories should also be considered.

CONCLUSIONS

The extractive sector is associated with several important environmental, social, and governance challenges and risks, which are often linked to or part of broader economic and political dynamics. Although important improvements in the environmental and social regulations implemented in Latin America and the Caribbean have been identified (specifically in Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, Panama, and Peru) aimed at promoting the role of the extractive sector as a catalyst for sustainable development, extractive activities in the region continue to cause environmental and social impacts, including cases of water, air, and soil pollution; deforestation; and loss of biodiversity (24). Considering that water resources management affects almost all aspects of the economy and in particular food production and security, public supply and sanitation, energy and industry, health and environmental sustainability (all impacted by climate change) if conducted inadequately, it will undermine the achievement of poverty reduction and development goals in all their dimensions, i.e. economic, social and environmental (25) and as a consequence also the implementation of the SDGs by the mining sector in the territories where it operates.

RECOMMENDATIONS

As the role of water is essential in the process of climate change, adaptive measures must be taken regarding management in national plans or international investment portfolios of the natural resource. For this purpose, significant investments and policy changes are necessary. It is recommended (in a joint and collaborative effort from local to global levels, within sectors, across sectors, as well as among multidisciplinary institutions) to consider the following principles: integrating adaptation into the context of broader development; strengthening governance and enhancing water resources management; improving and sharing knowledge and information on climate change, as well as investing in data collection; building long-term resilience through stronger institutions and investment in infrastructure and ecosystem balance; investing in effective and adaptive water management, as well as technology transfer (25).

For an integrated, multi-sectoral and multidisciplinary response to the issue, we should take as our guiding principle the regenerative development^{xi} and the role of the state as mediator of the different interests, ensuring as a *sine qua non* condition for the sustainability of development, the real participation of civil society in the management of water and territory as a whole. In the case of Brazil, it is recommended to advance with the implementation of Ecological-Economic Zoning (26; 27) aiming to overcome the limitations already identified in the process (28). And, in line with the goal of climate neutrality by 2050, we should promote the transition from the linear economy to the circular economy^{xii}, i.e., from extraction/production/consumption/disposal to repair/reuse/remanufacture/recycle allowing raw materials introduced into production chains to maintain, or even increase, their value. In the case of Brazil, we should move forward with the approval of Bill No. 1874 of 2022, which establishes the National Policy of Circular Economy, as one of the ways to face the problem of growing consumption and decreasing availability of raw materials and inputs.

From the perspective of the co-evolution between the socioeconomic and environmental systems, the ZEE and the Circular Economy are placed as tools that will enable the States (under the performance of national and international interagencies for monitoring the governmental and corporate commitment to human and environmental rights) to strategically plan the regenerative territorial development in order to implement the 17 SDGs (including therein the contribution of the mineral sector) and ensure climate adaptation.

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ⁱⁱ In Brazil, one of Vale's actions is the Sossego metallurgical plant in the state of Pará, where 99.99% of the water used to produce copper concentrate is recycled from the settling basin and recirculated through the processing circuit. The procedure saves 900,000 cubic meters of freshwater per year, which was previously pumped from a nearby river, enough water to supply a city of 25,000 inhabitants for six months. The only freshwater the facility uses is potable water (31).

ⁱⁱⁱ Through the Geological Mapping of the Territory Program (2003; 2010-2011) the Minas Gerais state government carried out the aerogeophysical study, finalized by Comig/SEDE-MG in 2013, completing 100% aerogeophysical coverage, with surveys distributed in 21 areas, with different degrees of priority. Map available at <http://www.portalgeologia.com.br/index.php/mapa/>. Accessed on Jun. 10th, 2023.

^{iv} The term Iron Quadrangle refers to a geological structure whose shape resembles a square and that makes up an area of approximately 12,000 km² located between Ouro Preto in the southeast and Belo Horizonte in the northwest (ROESER e ROESER, 2010 apud BRASIL: 2022, p. 46).

^v The *cangas* are rocky coverings that constitute a unique geosystem. These rocks have porosity and structure that facilitate the deep penetration of rainwater. During this process the water is naturally filtered and is stored below the surface, where the ore is, forming a huge water reservoir or aquifer. The basins that today supply 45% of the Metropolitan Region of Belo Horizonte – RMBH and 60% of the capital Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais depend on the spring that rises in the Serra do Gandarela. In areas where iron ore is mined, however, this *canga* layer is blown away and discarded as 'waste material', compromising the water recharge process and contaminating the underlying aquifer reserve (BECKER: 2017).

^{vi} In August 2009, the resistance movements to the mining enterprise in the Iron Quadrangle region assembled for an integrated action in defense of the Serra do Gandarela, officially creating the Movement for the Preservation of the Serra do Gandarela with the participation of different institutions. As available on the MPSG website: https://www.facebook.com/pg/preservegandarela/about/?ref=page_internal. Accessed on Jun. 12th, 2023.

^{vii} The Serra do Gandarela National Park is in the Municipalities of Nova Lima, Raposos, Caeté, Santa Barbara, Mariana, Ouro Preto, Itabirito and Rio Acima, State of Minas Gerais (31).

^{viii} At the public hearing, held on March 7, 2023, in Conceição do Mato Dentro to discuss the impacts of mining on water resources, the serious problems that the 13 affected communities are still experiencing due to the scarcity of water were highlighted, revealing the failure to solve the issue 15 years after the implementation of the Minas-Rio project. Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CTW6jNyzOIk>. Accessed on Jun. 21st, 2023.

^{ix} Already impacted by the collapse of the mining tailings dam called Fundão, controlled by Samarco Mineração S.A in partnership with Vale S.A and the Anglo-Australian BHP Billiton, which occurred on November 5, 2015 in the sub district of Bento Rodrigues, 35 km from the center of the municipality of Mariana, MG, causing the greatest environmental impact in Brazilian history and the largest in the world involving tailings dams, with a total dumped volume of 62 million cubic meters. The mud reached the Rio Doce, whose watershed covers 230 municipalities in the states of Minas Gerais and Espírito Santo.

^x Anglo-American aims, based on its Sustainable Mining Plan, to enter a partnership with the Port of Açú to study the reuse of water used in the operation of the Minas-Rio project pipeline in industrial units of the complex (current and future) so that gradually, the effluent generated by the filtering system is no longer discarded into the sea as it is today. According to the company, water reuse can potentially reach 0.3 m³/s of reused water (33).

^{xi} Regenerative development refers to the use of resources to improve the quality of life of society in a way that builds the capacity to regenerate and maintain the conditions necessary for the evolution of living systems, human and otherwise (30).

^{xii} In the Circular Economy, the inputs, products, and waste produced fall either into technical or biological cycles. Technical cycles reinsert products and their parts, while biological cycles reintroduce biological nutrients in a safe way.